

The Sense Annotation of BulTreeBank

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Abstract

The paper focuses on the sense annotation of BulTreeBank. It discusses three levels of annotation: valency frames, lexical senses and DBPedia URIs. The lexical sense annotation is considered in more detail and in relation to the other two processes. Special attention is paid to the quality validation with respect to two aspects: inter-annotator agreement and cross-resource control.

1 Introduction

Treebanks are typically considered as syntactically annotated corpora. However, the recent tendencies have shown that at some point they actually turn into knowledge-rich resources with semantic and discourse information. The most canonical example for this is the development of Penn Treebank into proposition and discourse treebanks. BulTreeBank was developed as a syntactically annotated corpus for Bulgarian, which currently exists in several formats: in its original format (HPSG-based) and in its conversions (dependency based [1]; Penn treebank based [3]; stanfordized [10]).

In this paper we present the methodology of sense annotation in the BulTreeBank original format. Our efforts have been invested in adding value at several levels, yielding three layers of sense annotation - of lexical senses, valency information and DBPedia instances. The annotation process involved extraction of valency frames from the treebank, addition of senses to verbs, nouns, adjectives and adverbs, as well as combining valency, DBPedia and sense annotation into one merged resource. Thus, the difference with sense annotation in non-treebank corpora is the availability of valency frames in the treebanks, which are used for support of the lexical sense annotation.

The paper is structured as follows: in section 2 the related works are mentioned; in section 3 the methodology of the sense annotation is described; section 4 presents our strategies for annotation quality control; section 5 concludes the paper.

2 Related Work

There are a number of resources which are sense annotated. Most of them rely on WordNets and/or other lexical resources that provide sense differentiation, such as language-specific lexicons. Sense annotated corpora take their origins from seminal corpora, such as SemCor, and are realized as particular variants of them in other languages, such as Dutch, Basque, Bulgarian, etc.¹ Unfortunately, most of them are not freely available in their full capacity and for further third-party research.

At the same time, there are not so many treebanks available that have been annotated with senses. Here the following ones need to be mentioned, among others: for English, the sense annotated developments of Penn Treebank — PropBank ([8]) and NomBank ([5]) — as well as OntoNotes, which combines sense information from several resources; for German, the TüBa-D/Z sense annotated treebank [4]; for Italian, the syntactic-semantic treebank [6]. In OntoNotes an ontology was used for mapping the WordNet senses. This is the Omega Ontology [9].

Our resource differs from PropBank and Prague Dependency Treebank in that it does not provide detailed semantic role labels. We expect this information to come from the ontological labels in valency frames over the grammatical roles (subject, complement, adjunct). The sense annotated BulTreeBank keeps closer to the OntoNotes strategy of combining syntactic analysis with sense annotations. We also use an ontology - DOLCE - for constraining the senses and controlling their granularity.

The novelty in our sense annotation endeavour lies, as far as we are aware, in the combination of assigned valencies, lexical senses and DBPedia URIs into a syntactic resource.

3 Sense Annotation

For the purposes of the sense annotation, three phases were envisaged: preparation, sense annotation and quality control. The first two phases were discussed in [11]. In the preparatory phase substantial efforts were invested into mapping the definitions of a Bulgarian explanatory dictionary to the intersected senses of Core and Base Concepts in Princeton WordNet. These amount to 5000. The mapping was done automatically with the help of a Bulgarian-English dictionary. Then, these mappings were manually checked and curated according to the following schema: selection of the correct sense among available ones; addition of a sense which is missing in the Bulgarian dictionary; update of a definition. We tried to provide richer definitions in comparison with the Princeton WordNet glosses, since we plan to use this information for enriching the ontology and cross-data relations.

The annotation process was organized in three layers: verb valency frames [7]; senses of verbs, nouns, adjectives and adverbs; DBPedia URIs over named

¹<http://globalwordnet.org/wordnet-annotated-corpora/>

entities. First, the valency frames of the verbs were extracted from the treebank with assigned ontological labels over the participants, and then checked manually.

The sense annotation was organized as follows: the lemmatized words per part-of-speech from the treebank got all their senses from the explanatory dictionary of Bulgarian and from our WordNet. When two competing definitions came from both resources - the preference went to the one that was mapped to the WordNet. In the ambiguous cases the correct sense was selected according to the context of usage. For the purpose of evaluation some of the files were checked by two people. More information on this is given in the next section. 92 000 running words have been mapped to senses from the WordNet. Thus, about 43 % of all tokens of the treebank have been covered.

After the manual checks, the sentences with the valency frames were merged with the added word senses. In this step several issues have been addressed: the valency frames have been generalized from the initial syntax surface realizations to argument structure lists, which contain also the potential participants in the event; the various senses have been mapped to the corresponding valency frames; any remaining inconsistencies have been fixed. Thus, the treebank initially provided specific verb frames, realized in the texts, and these were later generalized with respect to participants, as well as senses.

The annotation with DBPedia URIs was performed as a separate activity, but closely related to the valency frames and sense annotation tasks. It covered 10 885 named entities — 2877 organizations, 2938 locations, 4195 people, the rest are from different categories: events, books, others. Unfortunately, the coverage of the Bulgarian DBPedia is rather small. For that reason, the the Bulgarian Wikipedia was used for adding the respective links into the data.

In the process of lexical sense annotation and DBPedia annotation, multi-word expressions have been handled as well. During sense annotation all the idiomatic expressions (idioms, light verb constructions, etc.) have been specifically labeled as multiword expressions, in contrast to the previously pure syntactic approach, taken in the annotation of the treebank. Since many of these expressions have a rather narrow potential for combination with other units, the differences show in the ontological constraints. This means that instead of labeling the participants of a predicate as high level concepts, such as Person, Cognitive Fact, Social Event, Machine, etc., the labels remain very specific. Here are two examples, in which the subject has more abstract constraints, while the complement remains specific: 'Litse/grupa ot litsa ostana bez pokriv', "PERSON/GROUP OF PERSONS remains/remain without roof" (PERSON/GROUP OF PERSONS becomes/become homeless); 'Materialni sredstva/deystvie/deynost otida na vy-atara', "MEANS/ACT/ACTIVITY goes to the wind" (MEANS/ACT/ACTIVITY is wasted).

During the DBPedia annotation process, the URIs were pointed to the full names of the entities, while the text box kept the specific occurrences of the names in the text. Several kinds of challenging situations were encountered: the text provides a metaphoric name for the entity, while the DBPedia link uses its real name

(for example, the politician Ahmed Dogan is referred to as Sokola (the Falcon) in many texts, but in DBPedia the link is constructed from his actual name); there is insufficient context for the selection of the correct URI; there is no matching URI in the Bulgarian DBPedia; there is no direct URI mapping to the name, available only under another URI.

In the following table some statistics is given on the number of tokens, lemmas and definitions annotated per part-of-speech. Also the ratios Token-to-Lemma and Definition-per-Lemma are presented.

	tok	lemma	def	Tok/Lemma	Def/Lemma
Adj	17741	2077	4344	08,5416	2,0915
Adv	7571	533	726	14,2045	1,3621
Noun	49658	3477	8046	14,2819	2,3141
Verb	17977	2058	5163	08,7352	2,5087
Total	92947	8145	18279		
Tok/Lemma	11,4115				
Def/Lemma	02,2442				

It can be seen that the largest POS group of annotated tokens is that of the Noun. Verbs and Adjectives are comparable to each other. Unsurprisingly, the adverbs constitute the smallest group. The same POS distribution holds for lemmas as well. As for the definitions, the POS hierarchy for their number per lemma in decreasing order is: **Verbs > Nouns > Adjectives > Adverbs**. Interestingly, the ratio Token-to-Lemma combines together Nouns and Adverbs, on the one hand, which both show lesser variety, and Adjectives and Verbs, on the other, which both exhibit greater variety. The definitions per lemma remain stable: with respect to Nouns, Adjectives and Verbs - around 2 definitions per lemma, and with respect to Adverbs - 1 definition.

4 Quality Control

This section discusses two perspectives on quality control: inter-annotator agreement and cross-resource control.

4.1 Inter-annotator Agreement

4.1.1 Naively-measured agreement vs. Case-based evaluation

An initial evaluation of inter-annotator agreement was carried out on a limited sample of sense-annotated sentences. The sample file contains 905 sentences, with one lemma of interest per sentence (the lemmas being only nouns starting with the letter A in this particular file). Out of these, 190 sentences present cases where

the two annotators have made different choices in the selection of word senses. Naively-measured inter-annotator agreement is 79%.

An examination of the entries where annotator choices differ, however, reveals that agreement is actually higher. This is due to the nature of the task and the availability, or rather the lack of, comprehensive lexical resources. Because of that, the range of selectable senses for each lemma does not always exhaust all possible meanings; and sometimes one and the same sense is expressed through two or more definitions (which usually come from different resources). Additionally, there is the issue of word senses overlapping in terms of meaning, or of word senses that are in a relation of hyponymy/hypernymy with one another. Therefore the annotators' task is not just that of making the relevant choices, but also of enriching the sets of possible definitions. Below we give an overview of these issues.

4.1.2 Word senses introduced by the annotators

There are many cases where a relevant word sense is missing from the array of available choices and the annotator therefore needs to supply additional ones (from external lexical resources, or construct them on their own). Alternatively, there could be a presupplied word sense that is suitable in a specific case, but it somehow falls short of best expressing the meaning in question, so once again the annotators are faced with the task of introducing an additional definition. Thus even if the two annotators have chosen imported word senses that convey roughly the same meaning, these constitute formally different choices. For instance, the word 'avtomat' (automaton) is tagged with three different senses among the two annotators, but these three are very close in meaning to one another; the three definitions roughly translate as: 1) an apparatus that performs certain actions on its own, 2) a device or mechanism that carries out the same task repeatedly, without any immediate human participation, 3) an apparatus with a mechanism that performs certain actions on its own, mimicking humans. In this case there is no actual disagreement between annotators, as they have both selected word senses that are very close to one another. In many cases only one annotator has added a word sense; the added definition outlines the same idea as a presupplied word sense, but more clearly and precisely. These cases too do not constitute real disagreement, they are rather an artifact of the annotation methodology. With some entries, of course, the annotator-introduced definitions do not actually map correctly to the contextual meaning of the words in question.

Out of the 380 items for annotation that were manually evaluated (2x190, i.e. the two identical sets of sentences), 113 constitute situations where an annotator has introduced a word sense not present in the presupplied options, i.e. 30%. The number is high, but it should be noted that some of the added definitions are introduced multiple times across items, as the same lemmas are annotated in different sentences.

4.1.3 Equivalent word senses coming from different resources

A similar source of apparent disagreement is when the presupplied word sense sets include very similar definitions, most often coming from different lexical resources. For instance, consider the word 'avans', when it appears in sports contexts (it translates to 'a lead (by points/goals/etc)'). One of the annotators has selected just one of the available senses, while the other has selected two of the options, the second being very close to the first one, though more economical in its wording. Such cases will be at some point normalized and made consistent with a common ontology. They do not constitute actual clashes between the annotators' choices.

4.1.4 Word senses with different granularity

Another reason for disagreement is differences at the level of concept granularity. In one sentence the word 'avtor' (author) is tagged with the more general sense of 'creator of a product' by one annotator and with the more specific sense of 'writer' by the other annotator. In another sentence, one annotator has chosen the more general sense, while the other has selected both the more general and the more specific, apparently unsure about the right answer. Sometimes one of the annotators has selected the more specific definition, while the other has selected only the more general; in the cases where context allows only the broader sense, this constitutes genuine inter-annotator disagreement. Some of these cases usually require a broader than sentence-scope context to disambiguate the meaning. In most cases looking at the paragraph containing the sentence is enough to solve the problem. Lemmas as the above-described one present difficulties when the more specific sense is not applicable, as well. For example, the author of a report cannot in Bulgarian be referred to as a writer (the Bulgarian analogue 'pisatel' is used chiefly to refer to authors of literature). In several places this has been the source of disagreement between the two annotators. Identifying such mismatches at the level of conceptual granularity is in itself a difficult task. A cursory examination revealed 13 such items, i.e. around 7% of all the manually examined sentences (or around 1% of the total number of sentences in the file).

4.1.5 Disagreement due to lack of context

There are occasions when even paragraph-scope context fails to support the process of word sense disambiguation. Discourse and world knowledge are needed to provide the relevant information. Consider a sentence which translates in English roughly as 'The three story building with two big *workshops* on 'Luben Karavelov' 15 will be turned into a Center for culture and debate called 'The Red House'.' The Bulgarian word used for 'workshop' ('atelier') has two related but different senses: one is of a small working room where artisans of all kinds carry out their work, the other is of the working space of a painter, sculptor, photographer (i.e. an artistic person). In this case one annotator has chosen the more general sense, while the other has selected the more specific. The paragraph where the sentence comes from

does not provide information sufficient to clarify which of the word senses is more appropriate. Reference to online sources reveals that the building was home to a famous sculptor who donated it to the state. This extra-textual piece of knowledge helps carry out the disambiguation. There are several other similar cases, although they are not many compared to the overall number of entries.

4.1.6 Complete disagreement between annotators

Last come the sources of difference where one annotator has simply made the better decision. Such cases present challenges of varying levels of difficulty to the annotators. For instance, one sentence where the annotators' choices differ contains the noun 'avtoritet' (authority). One option is to annotate it with the sense of 'the quality of having authority'; an alternative sense is 'a person commanding authority'. The right choice is fairly straightforward in the context of the sentence and the mistake of one of the annotators may probably be attributed to a momentary lapse of focus.

In other cases, however, the task is more complicated. For example, there is a sentence that could be translated in two different ways: 1) 'In this way the airport will meet the highest *aviation* standards, said Noev.' and 2) 'In this way the airport will meet the highest standards of *the national aviation*, said Noev.' That is, it is left unclear whether by 'aviatsiya' (aviation) is meant aviation as an occupation and field of activity (with its attendant international standards) or some local aviation organization (in this case the corresponding Bulgarian entity). This calls for a more subtle disambiguation thought-process.

4.1.7 Summary of the evaluation task

Out of the 190 sentences that are annotated differently by the annotators, 95 have been classified as instances of full inter-annotator disagreement. In 42 sentences there is partial conceptual overlap between the two annotators' choices, i.e. at least one annotator has selected more than one word sense and at least one word sense option has been selected in both annotated versions, but there are additional differences in the selections. 52 sentences have been annotated with different word sense definitions that are however roughly equivalent in terms of meaning (differing mostly with respect to phrasing). There is 1 sentence where the annotators have both made correct choices but one has selected the more general sense and other the more specific. Thus, out of the 190 items where annotators apparently disagree with each other, full disagreement is observed in 50% of the cases, partial disagreement in 22% of the cases, and in 27% of the cases exhibiting apparent inter-annotator disagreement the annotators have actually selected (almost) identical word senses. A less strict evaluation approach thus gives 90% inter-annotator agreement. The nature of the task makes evaluation difficult but insightful with regards to how an ontology of word senses should be structured. Unfortunately, due to the above-described noisiness of the data, calculating more sophisticated

scores of inter-annotator agreement (e.g. Cohen's kappa) is very difficult, if at all possible.

4.2 Cross-resource control

Another way of ensuring the quality of the annotation is through the combination of annotation levels. Two types of such combination were carried out: of verb valency frames and sense annotations, on the one hand, and of DBPedia URIs and valency frames, on the other.

Since the participants in the treebank-driven valence dictionary were mapped to WordNet and the DOLCE ontology, we also get control over the other parts-of-speech. For example, the perfective verb 'izbroya' (count) has three valency frames from the valence dictionary. They happen to share one meaning. The frames are: to count COGNITIVE FACTS; to count PERSONS; PERSON counts PERSONS. It can be noted that the first two frames do not include restrictions on the subject, while the third one does. These frames are generalized into a frame that considers also the subject participant. It says: PERSON counts OBJECTS.

Another issue that benefits from the cross-resource control is the usage of perfective/imperfective verbs. The merging of valency frames with senses shows the preferences (based on frequencies) of the perfective and/or imperfective verb to be used with a specific frame and/or sense.

In this way all the valency frames are: 1. mapped to their senses and 2. generalized into coarse frames, if necessary. At the moment around 1050 verb frames have been processed in this way.

The DBPedia URIs annotation is considered in relation to valency frames and senses. The labels that mark the participants in the frame come from the DOLCE ontology. The senses mapped to the WordNet inherit ontological constraints from two ontologies - DOLCE and SUMO. DBPedia annotations follow the DBPedia ontology. All these ontologies need to be synchronized for the sake of resource consistency and utility.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we present the methodology behind sense annotation in BulTreeBank. The scheme relies on the annotation of verb valency frames, sense annotation of four parts-of-speech (nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs) and DBPedia URIs. The advantage of such a strategy is that the cross-reference of valence-to-senses (including DBPedia links) can also be used as a controlling mechanism to ensure the quality of the resulting resource, with respect to the integration of lexical semantics with valency, real world facts and ontological mappings.

A closer examination of inter-annotator agreement in fact shows higher integrity than the surface numbers appear to indicate. This is due to some quasi-problematic mismatches.

Our efforts reported in the paper are similar to the sense annotation task performed by [2] for English, but with some differences, such as: only Core WordNet with Bulgarian sense lexicon has been used for the annotation; the annotation was performed on a treebank, which provided the facility of using a derived valence lexicon and available grammatical roles; no confidence markers have been used by the human annotators - the superannotation technique and cross-resource mappings were adopted as quality assurance strategies instead; DBPedia links have been added.

After the cross-reference stage is performed, the treebank will be made publicly available for research use. The mapping of senses and DBPedia URIs to a formal ontology will provide a basis for the combination of sentence-based semantic analysis with links to world knowledge.

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